

KEY INDICATORS

With 269,080 hectares (2024), Slovakia had 14.1% of its farmland under organic management. Growth from 2001-2024 was modest, with the organic farmland more than quadrupled. Retail sales data is not available for Slovakia.

ORGANIC FARMLAND

2001

2024

Area* (Share of Total Farmland)

58,706 ha (2.7%)

269,080 ha (14.1%)

Area Growth from 2001 to 2024

358.35%

ORGANIC LAND USE & AQUACULTURE

2001

2024

Arable Land* (Share of Total)

N/D

88,683 ha (6.6%)

Permanent Crops* (Share of Total)

N/D

2,457 ha (13.9%)

Grassland* (Share of Total)

N/D

177,941 ha (34.3%)

Aquaculture Production (Share of Total)

N/D

N/D

ORGANIC OPERATORS

2001

2024

Producers (Share of Total)

82 (0.1%)

1,750 (8.9%)

Aquaculture Producers

N/D

N/D

Processors

N/D

151

Importers

N/D

67

ORGANIC RETAIL SALES

2001

2024

Retail Sales (Share of Total)

N/D

N/D

Per Capita Consumption

N/D

N/D

Retail Sales Growth from 2001 to 2024

N/D

Imports

N/D

1,157 †

Source: FiBL survey based on national data sources, Eurostat and TRACES/European Commission in the framework of the OrganicTargets4EU project

*In conversion and fully organic

KEY INDICATORS

DEVELOPMENT OF ORGANIC FARMLAND IN SLOVAKIA

Source: FiBL-AMI Survey, Eurostat, Nic Lampkin

CAP ORGANIC POLICY SUPPORT

The Slovakia CAP strategic plan provides for a 70% increase in supported organic area and a more than doubling of expenditure compared with 2018. Planned maintenance payments are increased by up to 50% compared with the previous period, and more than doubled for selected horticultural crops. The net effect of increased area and payment rates is a 24% increase in average expenditure per ha. There is no differentiation between conversion and maintenance payments.

CONVERSION & MAINTENANCE

	2018	2025	2027
Land Area Supported (Change from 2018)*	158 kha	283 kha	270 kha (+71%)
Share of Total Agricultural Area Supported*	8.2%	15.9%	14% (+71%)
Share of Certified Organic Area Supported (Change)*	84%	97%	N/D
Expenditure per Year*	17 M€	39 M€	36 M€ (+112%)
Expenditure per Hectare Supported*	108 €	136 €	134 € (+24%)

SHARE OF CAP RESOURCES

CAP EXP. 2023-2027 ORGANIC SHARE*

Organic Farming Support (P2)*	180 M€	100%
Eco-Schemes (P1)	559 M€	15%
Agri-Environment, Climate, Welfare (P2)	642 M€	
Total CAP Expenditure	4,097 M€	4.4%

*including in-conversion and fully organic land

CAP ORGANIC CONVERSION AND MAINTENANCE PAYMENTS FOR DIFFERENT LAND USES

INDICATOR	YEAR	FUND	GRASSLAND	ARABLE CROPS	HORTICULTURE	FRUIT CROPS	GRAPES
Conversion Support (€/ha)	2023	P2	96	170	795	497-904	762
	2025	P2	127	170	795	497-1111	468-762
Change from 2023 to 2025			32%	0%	0%	23%	0%
Maintenance Support (€/ha)	2023	P2	96	170	795	497-904	762
	2025	P2	127	170	795	497-1111	468-762
Change from 2023 to 2025			32%	0%	0%	23%	0%
Conversion Support Higher than Maintenance	2023	P2	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
	2025	P2	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%

P1 (Pillar 1) European Agricultural Guarantee Fund (EAGF); P2 (Pillar 2) European Agricultural Fund for Rural Development (EAFRD) and national co-financing

NATIONAL ORGANIC ACTION PLAN

Slovakia had two organic action plans between 1995 and 2010 and was one of the earliest current EU Member States to adopt this approach. But there was then a long gap before the current plan, so only this plan has been analysed. To support the land area target of 14% of UAA by 2027, the plan emphasises supply chain development, public procurement and catering initiatives as well as basic information measures.

TARGETS

	PERIOD	LAND AREA TARGET	OTHER TARGETS
Previous Action Plan	No recent plan	None	None
Current Action Plan	2023-27	14% of UAA by 2027	None

KEY ACTIONS

PREVIOUS ACTION PLAN (NO RECENT PLAN)

CURRENT ACTION PLAN (2023 - 2030)

AQUACULTURE

The organic share of total aquaculture production in Slovakia is negligible, and there is no reference to aquaculture in the current action plan. Slovakia was not included in our analysis of the EMFF (2014-2020) and EMFAF (2021-2027) operational programmes and the Multi-annual National Strategic Plan for Aquaculture. If any support is provided, the funding is project specific and there is no ring-fenced organic budget, so statistics on organic aquaculture support expenditure are not available.

OrganicTargets4EU
www.organictargets.eu

Project Coordinator
Ambra De Simone
IFOAM Organics Europe
www.organicseurope.bio

Authors
Helga Willer
(FiBL, Switzerland)

Nicolas Lampkin
(Thünen-Institut, Germany)

Sabine Reinecke
(FiBL, Switzerland)

Design
CONSULAI

Publication year
2026

